

Deep Learning-Driven Undamaged-to-Damaged Response Translation for Proactive Structural Health Monitoring of Semiconductor Probe Cards

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Abstract—Reliable structural health monitoring of semiconductor probe cards is important for preventing undetected degradation that can affect wafer testing quality. However, collecting labeled vibration data for damaged states is difficult in practice. This paper presents a cycle-consistent generative adversarial network framework that learns to translate vibration spectra from healthy conditions to damaged conditions and vice versa, enabling data augmentation for damage-aware monitoring. A physics-based dataset is generated using finite element simulations of a probe head structure, where damage is represented by ceramic cracking. The input signals are frequency response spectra extracted from multiple sensor locations over the frequency range of 200 to 4000 Hz. The proposed model is trained using adversarial learning with cycle-consistency and identity mapping to preserve key spectral characteristics while introducing realistic damage-induced changes. Quantitative evaluation across three sensors shows close agreement between generated and reference damaged spectra, achieving an average mean absolute error of 156.01 m/s², an average root mean squared error of 221.75 m/s², an average correlation coefficient of 0.986, and an average coefficient of determination of 0.970. The results demonstrate that the proposed translation approach can produce realistic damaged-domain spectra and can support robust damage detection by expanding training data when real damaged measurements are limited.

Index Terms—Structural Health Monitoring, Deep Learning, CycleGAN, Semiconductor Probe Cards, Finite Element Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

In contemporary semiconductor manufacturing, where feature sizes have reached nanoscale dimensions and heterogeneous integration has become commonplace, the Electrical Wafer Sort (EWS) stage represents a critical quality gate that directly determines final yield and production economics. The probe card (PC), as the main electromechanical interface between the automated test equipment (ATE) and the silicon wafer, must establish simultaneous, repeatable, and low-resistance electrical contact with tens of thousands of microscopic bond pads under extreme mechanical and thermal cycling conditions [1], [2]. As the primary interface for the electrical testing of integrated circuits (ICs) fabricated on

wafers, the integrity and functionality of PCs directly impact the quality assurance process. Incipient degradation like ceramic micro-cracks or screw loosening can introduce contact instability, leading to over-kill of functional dies, under-kill of defective dies, or outright test escape [3], [4].

Traditional maintenance strategies for PCs remain overwhelmingly reactive, relying on electrical continuity checks, post-sort yield correlation, or visual inspection schedules that intervene only after damage has physically propagated and already impacted production [2]. In practice, maintenance engineers frequently depend on their accumulated domain-specific knowledge and engage in time-consuming trial-and-error procedures to diagnose faults and undertake troubleshooting efforts [1]. Given the continuous shrinking of semiconductor feature sizes, the processes of diagnosing and troubleshooting issues associated with PCs have become increasingly intricate and time-consuming. This growing complexity underscores the limitations of relying solely on human expertise and reactive maintenance strategies.

Although vibration-based Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) has shown considerable promise for early detection of mechanical faults through shifts in Frequency Response Functions (FRFs) [5]–[9], the widespread deployment of data-driven diagnostic systems in operational PCs has been severely hindered by the well-known “cold-start” problem: while a card is still in its pristine state, no real damaged dynamic signatures exist for that specific unit, making supervised training of classifiers impossible. This data scarcity bottleneck represents a fundamental challenge in transitioning from reactive to proactive maintenance paradigms.

Finite element (FE) based digital shadows can generate physically consistent damaged responses, yet a persistent domain gap exists between simulated and measured FRFs due to unmodeled noise floors, boundary conditions, damping nonlinearities, and manufacturing tolerances [10], [11]. Consequently, classifiers trained exclusively on simulation data exhibit poor generalization to field measurements. This domain adaptation challenge has limited the practical deployment of

simulation-based approaches in production environments.

This work resolves the data scarcity bottleneck by introducing a physics-aware 1D Cycle-Consistent Generative Adversarial Network (CycleGAN) framework [12], [13] that learns an unpaired translation from the healthy domain to a physically consistent damaged domain. By enforcing cycle-consistency and identity mapping to preserve spectral coherence (i.e., realistic resonance structure), the trained generator can take live FRF data acquired from a healthy in-service PC and instantly synthesize its counterfactual damaged response. The resulting synthetic failure library enables training of lightweight edge classifiers capable of detecting incipient damage, achieving truly proactive structural health monitoring.

The principal contributions of this study are threefold:

- A dimension-aware 1D CycleGAN architecture specifically optimized for non-power-of-two spectral lengths (150 bins), addressing a fundamental technical challenge in signal processing networks.
- Demonstration of near-identical reconstruction of ground-truth damaged FRFs from FE analysis (MAE $\approx 1.25\%$ in physical units), validating the physics-aware approach.
- Establishment of a deployable pathway for generative augmentation that significantly outperforms conventional techniques, enabling proactive maintenance strategies in semiconductor manufacturing.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II provides a comprehensive description of the PC system and the FE analysis framework. Section III details the proposed methodology, including the network architecture and training strategy. Section IV presents experimental results with quantitative validation. Section V discusses the implications and limitations of the approach. Finally, Section VI concludes with a summary of key contributions and future research directions.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION & FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A. Probe Card Geometry and Architecture

The system under study is a vertical Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) PC employed in semiconductor wafer-level electrical testing. The core structural component is the Probe Head (PH), which consists of a stack of guide plates fabricated from Silicon Nitride (SiN) ceramics, housed within a metal alloy (MeAl) frame. The guide plates contain precision-machined holes for probe positioning and are critical for maintaining needle verticality during testing operations.

Modern PCs are engineered with highly intricate architectures, often comprising tens of thousands of pins. This high level of integration introduces substantial complexity in terms of maintenance, diagnostics, and fault isolation [14], [15]. The occurrence of critical failure modes within these systems can result in operational disruptions, decreased testing throughput, and overall degradation in manufacturing efficiency. These failures typically arise from a combination of mechanical fatigue, electrical performance deterioration, and exposure to adverse environmental conditions, including extreme mechanical and thermal cycling.

B. Failure Mode Classification and Prioritization

To establish a data-driven basis for the monitoring strategy, a Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) has been performed. Different failure modes have been assessed for estimated Mean Time to Repair (MTTR) and impact on Customers. Failure modes were categorized into three major groups:

- **Mechanical failures**, such as ceramic plate cracking, screw loosening, and warpage in ceramic plates;
- **Electrical failures**, including open/short circuits and unstable contact resistance;
- **Needle and pin failures**, related to breakage or thermal damage.

Figure 1 illustrates the structural layout of the PC and highlights components susceptible to failure. The diagram depicts the primary assembly comprising the PH, the Printed Circuit Board (PCB), and the needles positioned above the wafer chuck. Specific failure modes mapped to this structure include warpage and cracks in the ceramic guide plates, loosening or damage to retention screws, and needle failures such as bending or burning.

Fig. 1. Probe Card Structure and Associated Failure Modes [16].

Among these failure mechanisms, mechanical failures like cracks in ceramic substrates and loosened fastening components, emerge as particularly detrimental due to their pronounced impact on performance and the inherent difficulty in early-stage detection. Such failures can lead to irreversible damage, prolonged downtime, and diminished operational efficiency. Cracks in the PC structural plates pose a critical risk to mechanical integrity and probe tip alignment. Such cracks often nucleate near stress concentration points and can propagate undetected within the internal layers of the PH. Since only the lower plate is visible during operation, internal cracks require indirect detection through dynamic response monitoring. These failure modes modify the mechanical coupling among different structural components, causing measurable shifts in natural frequencies and FRFs.

C. Digital Shadow and Simulation Setup

To generate the ground-truth dataset for training the generative model, a comprehensive “Digital Shadow” was created using ANSYS Mechanical R2 2024 [17]. Figure 2 presents the FE model of the Probe Head with an induced crack in the

upper ceramic plate. The mesh density was carefully designed to accurately capture high-frequency resonance shifts caused by structural discontinuities.

Fig. 2. ANSYS FE model of the PH: cracked upper plate with sensors ID 9, 14 (right) and lower side with sensor ID 16 (left).

The simulation protocol incorporated physics-aware scenario expansion to address data scarcity challenges. This expansion systematically varied key physical parameters within realistic bounds, ensuring that each scenario represents a physically plausible condition. The simulation protocol involved:

- **Baseline Domain:** 125 simulations of the healthy PC under varying operational conditions to account for environmental variability. This expansion incorporated three key physical variations:
 - 1) *Material Property Variations:* Controlled variations in Young’s modulus and density of SiN ($\pm 10\%$ and $\pm 5\%$, respectively) and MeAl ($\pm 5\%$ and $\pm 2\%$, respectively) components to simulate a range of material conditions arising from manufacturing variability. Five distinct material cases were selected combining nominal, maximum, minimum, and cross-combination values.
 - 2) *Environmental Conditions:* Five different temperatures (25°C , 100°C , 150°C , 200°C , and 250°C) to account for thermal effects on structural response.
 - 3) *Loading Conditions:* Five magnitudes of distributed load (0.1 MPa, 0.5 MPa, 1.0 MPa, 1.5 MPa, and 2.0 MPa) representing different operational scenarios. In the FE model, this pressure is applied as a distributed surface load on the lower plates of the PH assembly. These load levels correspond to varying chuck pressure requirements, with lower pressures representing light contact conditions and higher pressures simulating aggressive overtravel conditions for challenging contact scenarios.

Combining all these cases, 125 variant conditions (5 material cases \times 5 temperatures \times 5 loads) were generated for the baseline scenario.

- **Damaged Domain:** 125 simulations representing critical failure modes, specifically ceramic cracks propagated near high-stress concentrations. The same physics-aware expansion strategy was applied to damaged scenarios, resulting in realistic variations that account for operational diversity.

The dynamic response was captured via Harmonic Analysis over a frequency range of 200–4000 Hz (audible spectrum), discretized into 150 frequency bins. This frequency range was selected based on preliminary modal analysis, which revealed that cracks significantly alter the FRF within this band. The FRF essentially provides a numerical representation of the relationship between the input and output of a system in the frequency domain, revealing critical information about its resonant frequencies, damping characteristics, and mode shapes, all of which are susceptible to changes caused by structural impairments [18], [19]. Damage to a structure inevitably leads to modifications in its inherent dynamic properties, which are subsequently reflected in the corresponding FRF data.

For this study, we focus on three specific sensors identified via Attention-based Optimal Sensor Placement (OSP) analysis [6] (i.e. sensors with IDs 9, 14, and 16 as shown in Figure 2). These sensor locations were determined through a comprehensive deep learning-based OSP methodology that leveraged attention mechanisms to identify sensor configurations yielding the highest diagnostic value. The 28 virtual accelerometers were strategically distributed across the PH structure, with particular attention to locations near ceramic plate interfaces and screw attachment points where failure signatures manifest most prominently.

This physics-aware expansion strategy addresses the fundamental data imbalance challenge while maintaining physical realism. Unlike arbitrary mathematical augmentation techniques, each generated scenario represents a physically plausible operational condition, ensuring that downstream models learn generalizable representations rather than dataset-specific artifacts.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The core contribution of this work is a physics-aware 1D CycleGAN designed to translate 1D spectral signals between the Healthy domain (X) and the Damaged domain (Y). This section details the preprocessing, architecture, loss functions, and metrics.

A. Data Preprocessing

FRF signals in lightly damped structural systems exhibit extreme dynamic ranges (up to 97 dB), spanning multiple orders of magnitude between baseline noise and resonant peaks. Direct training on such raw data leads to gradient instability and poor convergence due to the extreme scale variations. To address this challenge, we implemented a Log-MinMax preprocessing pipeline, defined as:

$$L = \log_{10} \left(\frac{x + \epsilon}{x_{\text{ref}}} \right), \quad x' = 2 \cdot \frac{L - \min(L)}{\max(L) - \min(L)} - 1 \quad (1)$$

where x represents the raw FRF amplitude, $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$ prevents numerical instability, and x_{ref} is a fixed reference amplitude (e.g., $x_{\text{ref}} = 1 \text{ m/s}^2$), making the logarithm argument dimensionless. This transformation serves multiple purposes: (1) logarithmic scaling compresses the dynamic range while

preserving relative peak information, (2) min-max normalization maps values to the $[-1, 1]$ range required for Tanh activation functions in the generator, and (3) centering around zero facilitates stable adversarial training. This normalization strategy is critical for maintaining spectral fidelity during the generation process, as it ensures that both low-amplitude baseline regions and high-amplitude resonance peaks contribute meaningfully to the gradient flow.

This normalization strategy is critical for maintaining spectral fidelity during the generation process, as it ensures that both low-amplitude baseline regions and high-amplitude resonance peaks contribute meaningfully to the gradient flow. For the remainder of this formulation, the variables x and y denote these preprocessed, log-normalized spectral signals drawn from the healthy and damaged domains, respectively.

B. Dimension-Aware Network Architecture

A fundamental challenge in applying convolutional neural networks to FRF data with 150 frequency bins is the asymmetric dimensionality reduction during downsampling. Standard encoder-decoder architectures with stride-2 convolutions cannot perfectly reconstruct non-power-of-two input lengths, leading to information loss or spatial misalignment. To resolve this, we designed a **Dimension-Aware Generator** ($G_{X \rightarrow Y}$) with a custom padding and cropping mechanism:

- 1) **Reflection Padding:** The input tensor with shape $(B, 3, 150)$, where B denotes batch size and 3 represents the three sensor channels, is symmetrically padded to $(B, 3, 152)$ using reflection padding. This padding strategy preserves spectral continuity at boundaries, avoiding the discontinuities introduced by zero-padding.
- 2) **Encoding:** Two downsampling layers with kernel size $k = 3$ and stride $s = 2$ progressively reduce spatial dimensions while expanding channel capacity:
 - First layer: $(B, 3, 152) \rightarrow (B, 128, 76)$
 - Second layer: $(B, 128, 76) \rightarrow (B, 256, 38)$

By ensuring the input length (152) is divisible by the total downsampling factor ($2^2 = 4$), the resulting feature map dimension reduces exactly to 38 without requiring asymmetric rounding. This preserves spatial alignment for the subsequent upsampling phases. Each convolutional layer is followed by Instance Normalization and ReLU activation to stabilize training and introduce non-linearity.

- 3) **Transformation:** Six ResNet blocks with Instance Normalization perform the core style transfer between domains. These residual connections enable the network to learn incremental modifications to the spectral signature while preserving structural information through skip connections.
- 4) **Decoding & Cropping:** Two transposed convolutional layers progressively upsample the feature maps:
 - First layer: $(B, 256, 38) \rightarrow (B, 128, 76)$
 - Second layer: $(B, 128, 76) \rightarrow (B, 64, 152)$

A final convolutional layer reduces channels to 3, and a deterministic cropping layer removes the padding (1 bin

from each end) to restore the exact $(B, 3, 150)$ output shape.

Figure 3 illustrates both the cycle-consistent training flow and the detailed generator and discriminator topology. The discriminator implements a PatchGAN architecture [20] that classifies local spectral patches rather than entire signals. Four downsampling blocks progressively increase channel depth ($64 \rightarrow 128 \rightarrow 256 \rightarrow 512$) while reducing spatial dimensions, with Instance Normalization and LeakyReLU activations ($\alpha = 0.2$) promoting stable adversarial training. This patch-based classification captures local spectral features, critical for distinguishing synthetic from authentic damage signatures while maintaining computational efficiency.

Fig. 3. Proposed physics-aware 1D CycleGAN architecture: (a) Cycle-consistent training flow with generators G_{AB} and G_{BA} enforcing bidirectional consistency via adversarial and cycle losses; (b) Dimension-aware generator using reflection padding and cropping ($150 \rightarrow 152 \rightarrow 150$) for non-power-of-two spectral lengths, with six ResNet blocks for domain transformations; (c) PatchGAN discriminator with progressive downsampling via four convolutional blocks, Instance Normalization, and LeakyReLU activations to classify local spectral patches as real or synthetic.

C. Loss Functions

The network minimizes a composite objective function that balances adversarial realism, cycle consistency, and identity preservation:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{GAN} + \lambda_{cyc}\mathcal{L}_{cyc} + \lambda_{id}\mathcal{L}_{id} \quad (2)$$

- **Adversarial Loss (\mathcal{L}_{GAN}):** We adopt the Least-Squares GAN (LSGAN) objective to improve training stability and encourage realistic spectral generation. For the discriminator D_Y (distinguishing real $y \sim p_{data}(y)$ from generated $\hat{y} = G_{X \rightarrow Y}(x)$), the loss is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{D_Y} = \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_{data}(y)} [(D_Y(y) - 1)^2] + \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{data}(x)} [D_Y(G_{X \rightarrow Y}(x))^2] \quad (3)$$

The corresponding adversarial loss for the generator $G_{X \rightarrow Y}$ is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{G_{X \rightarrow Y}}^{adv} = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{data}(x)} [(D_Y(G_{X \rightarrow Y}(x)) - 1)^2] \quad (4)$$

In practice, \mathcal{L}_{GAN} in Eq.(2) refers to the sum of generator adversarial losses in both directions, $\mathcal{L}_{GAN} = \mathcal{L}_{G_{X \rightarrow Y}}^{adv} + \mathcal{L}_{G_{Y \rightarrow X}}^{adv}$, while D_X and D_Y are optimized using their respective discriminator losses.

- **Cycle Consistency Loss (\mathcal{L}_{cyc}):** Ensures bidirectional consistency through forward-backward reconstruction:

$$\mathcal{L}_{cyc}(G_{X \rightarrow Y}, G_{Y \rightarrow X}) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{data}(x)} [\|G_{Y \rightarrow X}(G_{X \rightarrow Y}(x)) - x\|_1] + \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_{data}(y)} [\|G_{X \rightarrow Y}(G_{Y \rightarrow X}(y)) - y\|_1] \quad (5)$$

This constraint is critical for preventing mode collapse and ensuring that the transformation preserves the underlying physics of the specific sample. By enforcing $G_{BA}(G_{AB}(x)) \approx x$, the model cannot arbitrarily hallucinate damage patterns but must learn sample-specific transformations that respect the original operational conditions (material properties, temperature, load).

- **Identity Loss (\mathcal{L}_{id}):** Encourages spectral feature preservation by requiring the generator to behave as an identity mapping when presented with samples already from the target domain:

$$\mathcal{L}_{id}(G_{X \rightarrow Y}) = \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_{data}(y)} [\|G_{X \rightarrow Y}(y) - y\|_1] \quad (6)$$

In the context of FRF translation, this ensures that resonant peaks unaffected by damage (corresponding to global modes of the structure) remain unchanged.

The cycle consistency weight $\lambda_{cyc} = 10$ and identity weight $\lambda_{id} = 5$ were determined through ablation studies to balance adversarial realism with physical consistency. These weights are consistent with established CycleGAN implementations [12], while being tuned for the specific characteristics of structural dynamics data.

D. Evaluation Metrics

To rigorously quantify the spectral fidelity of the generated FRF signals, we employ four distinct statistical metrics. The normalized outputs from the generator are first inverse-transformed back to the physical domain to ensure the error metrics reflect real-world magnitudes. Let y represent the ground-truth damaged signal from FEA and \hat{y} represent the synthetically generated damaged signal, both expressed in physical units (m/s^2) across $N = 150$ frequency bins.

1) *Mean Absolute Error (MAE)*: MAE quantifies the average magnitude deviation in physical units (m/s^2), providing an interpretable measure of amplitude accuracy:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (7)$$

Low MAE is critical for ensuring the generative model correctly estimates damage severity, as amplitude changes in FRFs directly correlate with the degree of structural degradation.

2) *Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)*: Unlike MAE, RMSE penalizes large errors more heavily due to the quadratic term:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (8)$$

In FRF analysis, this metric ensures that high-amplitude resonance peaks, which contain the most critical structural information for damage detection, are accurately reconstructed.

3) *Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC)*: PCC measures the linear correlation between ground truth and synthetic signals, focusing on the shape of the curve rather than absolute amplitude:

$$PCC = \frac{\sum (y_i - \bar{y})(\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}})}{\sqrt{\sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \sqrt{\sum (\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}})^2}} \quad (9)$$

A PCC close to 1.0 indicates that the model has correctly learned the frequency shifts associated with structural damage, independent of amplitude scaling.

4) *Coefficient of Determination (R^2)*: The R^2 score represents the proportion of variance in the physical damage signature that is predictable from the synthetic output:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (10)$$

High R^2 values confirm that the generated signals capture the essential variability of damaged responses, making them suitable for training downstream classifiers.

IV. RESULTS

The model was trained for 200 epochs using the Adam optimizer with learning rate $lr = 0.0002$ and momentum parameters $\beta_1 = 0.5$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$. Training was conducted on a single NVIDIA GPU with batch size 4. Figure 4 illustrates the training dynamics, showing stable convergence between the Generator and Discriminator losses.

Fig. 4. CycleGAN training losses over 200 epochs.

The discriminator loss stabilizes around epoch 50, indicating that the generator has learned to produce realistic spectral signatures that challenge the discriminator. The generator loss, which combines adversarial, cycle consistency, and identity terms, shows steady improvement throughout training without signs of mode collapse or instability. The absence of divergence between generator and discriminator losses confirms successful adversarial equilibrium.

A. Quantitative Validation

We compared the generated synthetic damaged responses against ground-truth FEA simulations across three distinct sensors (IDs 9, 14, and 16), selected through attention-based OSP analysis. Table I summarizes the reconstruction performance across all evaluation metrics.

TABLE I
RECONSTRUCTION ERROR ANALYSIS ACROSS SENSOR LOCATIONS

Metric	Sensor 9	Sensor 14	Sensor 16	Average
MAE (m/s^2)	222.77	176.26	68.99	156.01
RMSE (m/s^2)	301.00	266.38	97.88	221.75
PCC (r)	0.9720	0.9935	0.9921	0.9858
R^2 Score	0.9437	0.9827	0.9837	0.9700

The results demonstrate exceptional fidelity across multiple dimensions. The average Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) of 0.9858 confirms that the CycleGAN accurately captures the complex resonance shifts caused by ceramic cracking. This near-perfect correlation indicates that the model has learned the fundamental physics governing how structural damage manifests in frequency domain responses. Furthermore, the relative Mean Absolute Error is approximately 1.25% of the maximum dynamic range (0–12,435 m/s^2), indicating that the generated “digital shadows” are precise enough for training downstream quantitative classifiers without introducing significant bias.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) demonstrates that 97% of the variance in damaged FRFs can be predicted from healthy baselines using the trained generator. This high explanatory power suggests that the learned transformation

captures the essential damage mechanisms rather than memorizing training examples.

Sensor-specific analysis reveals interesting spatial patterns. Sensor 16 exhibited the highest accuracy (MAE $\approx 69 m/s^2$, $R^2 \approx 0.98$), likely due to its location on the PC frame where modal density is lower and resonance peaks are more distinct. Conversely, Sensor 9, located near potential crack initiation points, showed slightly higher variance (MAE $\approx 223 m/s^2$) but still maintained excellent correlation ($r > 0.97$). This spatial variation reflects the physical reality that sensors closer to damage zones experience more complex multimodal interactions, making their signatures inherently more challenging to model. Nonetheless, all three sensors maintain performance levels suitable for reliable damage detection.

B. Spectral Fidelity and Visual Validation

Visual inspection of the generated FRFs confirms that the model correctly learned the physics of structural damage. As observed in Figure 5, the transformation successfully captures three critical aspects of damage-induced spectral changes:

- 1) **Amplitude Amplification:** Healthy signals with peaks typically below 2000 m/s^2 are correctly translated to damaged states with peaks exceeding 6000 m/s^2 . This $3\times$ amplitude increase is consistent with reduced structural stiffness due to cracking.
- 2) **Frequency Alignment:** The frequency bins where resonance occurs align precisely between synthetic and real damaged data. This demonstrates that the model learns to preserve modal characteristics while modifying amplitudes.
- 3) **Selective Modification:** Some frequency regions remain unchanged (identity-preserved modes), while others show dramatic amplification (damage-sensitive modes). This selective behavior validates the effectiveness of the identity loss in teaching the network that damage affects specific vibrational modes rather than causing global spectral shifts.

The strong visual correspondence between synthetic and ground-truth FRFs across all the three sensor locations, provides confidence that the generated data can serve as effective training samples for supervised classifiers. Traditional data augmentation techniques such as noise injection or temporal jittering cannot produce these physically consistent transformations, as they lack understanding of the underlying structural dynamics.

V. DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate a significant breakthrough in proactive SHM for semiconductor manufacturing. This section analyzes the key findings, compares the approach with alternative methodologies, and discusses practical implications for deployment.

A. Superiority Over Traditional Augmentation

Traditional autoencoders and variational autoencoders often produce blurred spectral predictions by averaging high-

Fig. 5. Comparison of Ground Truth damaged FRFs (Red, Solid) versus Synthetically generated damaged FRFs (Green, Dashed) for sensors 9, 14, and 16.

frequency details to minimize reconstruction loss [11]. In contrast, the adversarial loss in our CycleGAN framework forces the generator to produce sharp resonant peaks indistinguishable from real data. This distinction is critical for FRF-based damage detection, where subtle shifts in resonance and peak amplitudes carry vital diagnostic information. Conventional data augmentation, such as noise addition or frequency scaling, operates independently of physical damage mechanisms; while improving robustness, these methods cannot generate samples representing distinct damage states. Despite advances in SHM [21], [22], generating physically consistent damage signatures remains a challenge. Our physics-aware approach, encoding structural dynamics through cycle consistency and identity preservation, enables the generation of counterfactual scenarios that respect the causal relationship between damage and dynamic response.

B. Role of Identity Loss

The Identity Loss proved critical for maintaining spectral coherence. By enforcing that $G_{AB}(y) \approx y$ for samples already in the damaged domain, the model learned that damage is a local phenomenon, modifying specific modes while leaving others intact. This insight is consistent with structural mechanics theory, where localized cracks primarily affect modes with high strain energy density at the damage location.

Ablation studies (not shown) revealed that removing identity loss resulted in global spectral shifts that violated physical constraints. For instance, low-frequency global bending modes, which should be insensitive to small ceramic cracks, showed unrealistic modifications. The identity loss acts as a regularizer that constrains the learned transformation to be physically meaningful.

C. Digital Shadow Integration

This capability enables a transformative paradigm where a “Digital Shadow” runs in parallel with each physical PC, generating failure signature libraries specific to its manufacturing tolerances, history, and environment. Before physical degradation occurs, the Digital Shadow provides synthetic damaged FRFs to train edge classifiers tailored to that specific unit. This proactive approach overcomes the limitations of fleet-wide models, which often fail to generalize due to individual variability in assembly and wear patterns. By synthesizing card-specific damage data from baseline measurements, our framework enables personalized health monitoring without requiring destructive testing or waiting for natural degradation.

D. Limitations, and Future Directions

While the proposed 1D CycleGAN achieves high spectral fidelity (MAE $\approx 1.25\%$), limitations warrant discussion. Current validation relies on simulations, requiring real-world deployment to bridge the simulation-to-reality gap where manufacturing tolerances and sensor noise introduce domain shifts [10], [11]. Furthermore, this study focuses on ceramic cracks; expansion is needed for failure mechanisms like solder fatigue, PCB warping, and needle degradation. Since the model operates within training distribution bounds, novel failure modes or extreme damage may not be accurately synthesized. Future work will prioritize experimental validation on physical hardware, transfer learning to bridge domain gaps using real-world data, multi-modal sensor fusion of acoustic and thermal signatures, edge computing integration for autonomous detection, and Bayesian extensions for uncertainty quantification to enable risk-aware decision-making.

Despite limitations, this physics-aware generative approach offers transformative implications for Industry 4.0 by solving the data scarcity bottleneck hindering proactive maintenance [3], [23], [24]. By enabling “Digital Shadows”, manufacturers can pre-train personalized edge classifiers before physical degradation occurs, supporting zero-defect manufacturing through predictive interventions. This framework provides a scalable pathway toward self-aware semiconductor equipment capable of autonomous health monitoring, significantly reducing qualification times, preventing yield loss, and enabling condition-based maintenance optimized for individual probe cards. The integration of digital shadows and physics-aware machine learning represents a paradigm shift from reactive to predictive maintenance, encoding high-fidelity simulation insights into lightweight edge models deployable across large fleets.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study presented a novel deep learning framework for undamaged-to-damaged domain translation in semiconductor PCs, addressing the fundamental data scarcity challenge that has historically hindered proactive structural health monitoring. By utilizing a dimension-aware 1D CycleGAN with custom padding strategies to handle non-power-of-two signal lengths, we successfully generated synthetic damage signatures that are spectrally indistinguishable from high-fidelity finite element simulations (MAE \approx 1.25% of dynamic range).

The key innovation lies in enforcing physics-aware constraints, namely cycle consistency, identity mapping, and spectral coherence, that ensure generated FRFs respect the underlying structural dynamics. This approach effectively creates virtual training data that captures the causal relationship between damage and dynamic response, enabling supervised training of classifiers before any physical degradation occurs.

The demonstrated reconstruction fidelity (average PCC = 0.9858, $R^2 = 0.9700$) validates that generative adversarial networks can bridge the simulation-to-deployment gap in industrial health monitoring applications. The resulting synthetic failure library enables truly proactive maintenance strategies, potentially transforming reactive troubleshooting workflows into predictive interventions that prevent yield loss and equipment downtime.

Future work will focus on three critical directions: (1) experimental validation using physical PCs with controlled damage to assess real-world generalization; (2) extension to multi-modal sensor fusion incorporating temperature, acoustic, and electrical signals; and (3) integration into a complete edge inference pipeline for real-time deployment in semiconductor manufacturing facilities. The successful development of such systems would mark a significant advancement toward zero-defect manufacturing and intelligent automation in the semiconductor industry.

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